

NOTES

**Co-ordination Chemistry of Quinquevalent Molybdenum-
Oxopentabromomolybdic (V) Acid and other
Oxobromo-Compounds**

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Various compounds¹⁻⁴ of the type $M_2^I[MoOBr_5]$ and $M^{II}[MoOBr_5]$ (where $M^I = NH_4^+$ and other univalent cations and $M^{II} =$ bivalent cations and also of other organic bases) have been reported, but nothing is known about the hypothetical acid $H_2[MoOBr_5]$ up till now.

However, we have isolated this hitherto unknown oxopentabromo molybdic acid (V) for the first time in our laboratory by the reduction of molybdenum trioxide with hydrobromic acid and then by passing pure and dry hydrogen bromide gas through this solution at low temperature. The compound appears in reddish brown crystals. The analytical results closely correspond to $H_2[MoOBr_5]$. From the solution obtained by reduction of molybdenum trioxide with hydrobromic acid we have also isolated another brown crystalline compound which closely corresponds to $Mo(OH)Br_4$, or, $MoOBr_3 \cdot HBr$. Estimation of molybdenum and bromine was carried out by usual procedure². Magnetic measurements were carried out in Guoy balance and these results are tabulated below—

Compound		Mo (%)	Br (%)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)
$H_2[MoOBr_5]$	Found	18.42	77.41	1.67
	Calc	18.68	77.84	
$Mo(OH)Br_4$	Found	22.07	73.72	1.64
	Calc.	22.18	73.91	

The 'Spin only' values clearly show that in these compounds molybdenum is quinquevalent and has d^1 configuration. Oxidation state of the metal in these cases was determined by ceric sulphate titration and the results confirm the quinquevalent state on the metal. Both these compounds undergo extensive hydrolysis in aqueous solution which have been revealed by preliminary investigations by conductivity measurements.

1. Angell, James and Wardlaw, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 2578.
2. H. K. Saha and A. K. Banerjee, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 45, 660.
3. E. A. Allen, B. T. Brisdem, D. A. Edwards, G. W. A. Fowles and R. G. Williams, *H. J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 4649.
4. Weinland and Knoll, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1905, 44, 81.

The compound $\text{Mo}(\text{OH})\text{Br}_4$ on heating in solid state at 300° in absence of air for about 2 hr. gives a red sublimate (not analysed) and leaves a reddish brown residue which on analysis was found to be $\text{H}_2[\text{MoOBr}_5]$. This has also been verified by thermogravimetric analysis. This is, therefore, suggested that the solid state decomposition of $\text{Mo}(\text{OH})\text{Br}_4$ undergoes the following reaction

The product MoOBr_3 might undergo further pyrolysis to give other products. Detailed investigations of these bromo compounds are in progress which will be reported later on.

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